

Probability Density of Left Ventricular Mechanical Power: derivation from metadata

Paolo Maccallini

September 2023

1 Introduction

Studies employing tilt table testing are usually accompanied by metadata including means and standard deviations of diastolic blood pressure (DBP), systolic blood pressure (SBP), and cardiac index (CI). But the correlations between these measures are rarely shared and raw data are commonly not publicly available. Therefore, it is not possible to calculate means and standard deviations of parameters obtained by arithmetic operations from the ones mentioned, as is the case of cardiac power index (CPI), which is given by mean arterial pressure (MAP) times CI. CPI is a measure of the mechanical power of the left ventricle, normalized to body surface area.

In this document, I propose a method for the determination of the probability density of CPI from means and standard deviations of DBP, SBP, and CI. I then apply this method to the study of CPI in myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome (ME/CFS). I show that, according to this analysis, CPI is significantly increased in ME/CFS patients compared to controls, in a supine position, according to the metadata from a 2018 study. On the other hand, CPI is the same in the two groups, after 25-30 minutes of orthostatic stress at 70 degrees.

The method here described obtains the missing correlations by imposing that CPI has a three-parameter lognormal distribution and that the distributions of CI, DBP, and SBP follow Gaussian laws. Several limitations of the method are discussed in the document.

2 Mechanical power of the left ventricle

If we assume that there is no shear stress at the interface between the ventricle and the blood, the mechanical work generated by the elementary force exerted by the ventricle wall on the blood, at point \mathbf{x} and time t , is

$$dW(\mathbf{x}, t) = p(\mathbf{x}, t)\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot d\mathbf{x}$$

where $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the pressure field inside the ventricle, $\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the normal unit vector, directed outward, and \mathbf{x} identifies a point of $S(t)$ with respect to a cartesian reference system. Therefore, the mechanical power generated by the ventricle (known as *cardiac power*) is

$$CP(t) = \int_{S(t)} p(\mathbf{x}, t)\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)dS$$

where $S(t)$ is the interior surface of the ventricle, and $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the fluid velocity vector field. This is the flux of $p(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ across $S(t)$, therefore the divergence theorem gives

$$CP(t) = \int_{V(t)} \text{div}(p(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t))dV$$

where $V(t)$ is the volume enclosed in $S(t)$. Since

$$\text{div}(p(\mathbf{x}, t)\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)) = p(\mathbf{x}, t)\text{div}(\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)) + \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \vec{\nabla}p(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

we can write

$$CP(t) = \int_{V(t)} p(\mathbf{x}, t) \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)) dV + \int_{V(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \vec{\nabla} p(\mathbf{x}, t) dV$$

Therefore, the work of the left ventricle during a cycle can be obtained by integration with respect to time:

$$W = \int_{\text{cycle}} P(t) dt = \int_{\text{cycle}} \int_{V(t)} p(\mathbf{x}, t) \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)) dV dt + \int_{\text{cycle}} \int_{V(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \vec{\nabla} p(\mathbf{x}, t) dV dt$$

While the first addend of the second hand has a mean value of $\cong 1.3 \text{ joule}$ (1), the second term has been estimated to have a mean value of $3.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ joule}$ in one study (2), therefore it can be considered negligible, which is equivalent to assume, as a first approximation, that $p(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{p}(t)$. So, we remain with

$$CP(t) = \bar{p}(t) \int_{V(t)} \operatorname{div}(\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)) dV = \bar{p}(t) \int_{S(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t) dV$$

Note that the flux of blood across $S(t)$ is different from zero only during ventricle filling (VF) and ventricle ejection (VE). Therefore, if we indicate \bar{p}_{VF} the pressure of the blood that enters the left ventricle through the mitral valve, during ventricle filling, and \bar{p}_{VE} the pressure of the blood that passes through the aortic valve during ventricular ejection, we can calculate the mechanical work performed by the left ventricle during a cycle:

$$W = \int_{\text{cycle}} CP(t) dt = \bar{p}_{VF} \int_{\Delta t_{VF}} \int_{S(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t) dV dt + \bar{p}_{VE} \int_{\Delta t_{VE}} \int_{S(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t) dV dt$$

where Δt_{VF} is the time of filling and Δt_{VE} is the time of ejection. If we now take into account the fact that the blood can be regarded as an incompressible fluid, we have

$$- \int_{\Delta t_{VF}} \int_{S(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t) dV dt = \int_{\Delta t_{VE}} \int_{S(t)} \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{x}, t) dV dt = V_{ED} - V_{ES} = \Delta V > 0$$

where ΔV is the difference between the maximum volume of the ventricle (at the end of the diastole), and the minimum one (at the end of the systole). Therefore, we conclude that the total mechanical work performed by the left ventricle during a cycle is

$$W \cong \Delta V (\bar{p}_{VE} - \bar{p}_{VF})$$

which is the formula commonly reported in textbooks for the net mechanical work of the left ventricle over a cycle (stroke work) (1). The change in volume is usually indicated as stroke volume (SV) and measured by echocardiography, while the change in pressure is estimated as

$$\bar{p}_{VE} - \bar{p}_{VF} = DBP + \frac{SBP - DBP}{3}$$

where DBP is the diastolic blood pressure, and SBP is the systolic one. This value is commonly referred to as *mean arterial pressure*:

$$MAP \triangleq DBP + \frac{SBP - DBP}{3}$$

Therefore the mechanical power of the left ventricle can be obtained as

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad CP = SV \times HR \times MAP = CO \times MAP$$

where HR stands for heart rate, and $CO = SV \times HR$ is the *cardiac output* (3). It is also common to normalize SV and CO with respect to the *body surface area* (BSA)¹ and to use the notation

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad SVI = \frac{SV}{BSA}, \quad CI = \frac{CO}{BSA}$$

where SVI is the *stroke volume index*, and CI is the *cardiac index*. The most used formula for BSA is $\frac{1}{60}\sqrt{M \times H}$, where M is body mass [kg] and H is height [cm] and the result is expressed in m^2 . The surface area of an average human is approximately $1.8 m^2$ (1). On the same line, we define the normalized mechanical power of the left ventricle, known as *cardiac power index*:

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad CPI = \frac{P}{BSA} = SVI \times HR \times \left(DBP + \frac{SBP - DBP}{3} \right) = CI \times \left(DBP + \frac{SBP - DBP}{3} \right)$$

If SV is expressed in ml , BP , and SBP are measured in $mmHg$, and HR is expressed in $minutes^{-1}$, to have P in watts we must multiply by the conversion factor

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad \frac{10^{-6}m^3}{ml} \times \frac{133Pa}{mmHg} \times \frac{min}{60s} = 2.21 \times 10^{-6} \frac{min}{mmHg \times ml} W$$

As an example, if we consider the values

$$DBP + \frac{SBP - DBP}{3} = 100 \text{ mmHg}, \quad SV = 80 \text{ ml}, \quad HR = 75 \frac{beats}{min}, \quad BSA = 1.82 \text{ m}^2$$

we obtain

$$CP = 600000 \frac{mmHg \times ml}{min} = 1.32 \text{ W}, \quad CPI = 329.67 \frac{mmHg \times L}{min} = 0.728 \frac{W}{m^2}$$

3 Methods

In this paragraph, I describe the statistical model used to derive the density of CPI from metadata (means and standard deviations) on DBP , SBP , and CI .

¹ The most used formula is the one due to $BSA = \frac{1}{60}\sqrt{M \times H}$, where M is body mass [kg] and H is height [cm] and the result is expressed in m^2 . The surface area of an average human is approximately $1.8 m^2$ (1). Ethier C, Simmons C. Introductory Biomechanics: Cambridge University Press, 2007.

3.1 Definitions and hypotheses on the distributions

Let us define the following random variables:

$$X_1 = SVI \times HR = CI, \quad X_2 = MAP, \quad X_3 = DBP, \quad X_4 = SBP, \quad Y = X_1 X_2$$

We assume as hypotheses that X_1, X_3, X_4 follow Gaussian distributions and we make the positions:

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad X_i = N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2), \quad i = 1, 3, 4$$

We have $X_2 = X_3 + \frac{X_4 - X_3}{3} = \frac{2}{3}X_3 + \frac{1}{3}X_4$ with $\frac{2}{3}X_3 \sim N\left(\frac{2}{3}\mu_3, \frac{4}{9}\sigma_3^2\right)$, $\frac{1}{3}X_4 \sim N\left(\frac{1}{3}\mu_4, \frac{1}{9}\sigma_4^2\right)$, therefore

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad X_2 = N(\mu_2, \sigma_2^2), \quad \mu_2 = \frac{2\mu_3 + \mu_4}{3}, \quad \sigma_2 = \frac{\sqrt{4\sigma_3^2 + \sigma_4^2 + 4\rho_{3,4}\sigma_3\sigma_4}}{3}$$

where $\rho_{3,4}$ is the correlation coefficient between X_3, X_4 .

Settings	M	F	DBP	SBP	CO	Ref
Morning, fasting, rest	24	0	Femoral artery, Hamilton manometer		Direct Fick method	(4)
Morning, light breakfast, rest, supine	23	3	Right radial artery, needle and manometer		Direct Fick method	(5)

Table 1. Summary of methods employed in a set of studies used in the present work to compute the correlation coefficients between DBP and SBP, and between CI and MAP; and to find the best fit for the distribution of CPI.

CI	DBP	SBP	MAP	CPI	$\rho_{3,4}$	$\rho_{1,2}$	M	F	Ref
3.89 (1.34)	70.87 (9.18)	127.33 (15.88)	89.69 (10.78)	355.57 (152.19)	0.79 [0.56, 0.90]	0.47 [0.08, 0.73]	24	0	(4)
3.66 (0.89)	71.16 (7.36)	134.88 (15.77)	92.4 (9.15)	337.15 (92.66)	0.63 [0.31, 0.82]	-	23	3	(5)
3.77 (1.13)	71.02 (8.21)	131.18 (16.07)	91.07 (9.97)	346.56 (125.6)	0.69 [0.51, 0.82]	0.30 [0.01, 0.54]	47	3	pool

Table 2. Hemodynamic parameters in healthy subjects at rest, expressed as mean (SD), and correlations expressed as mean [95CI]. CI: cardiac index ($L/min/m^2$); DBP: diastolic blood pressure (mmHg); SBP: systolic blood pressure (mmHg); MAP: mean arterial pressure (mmHg); CPI: cardiac power index ($mmHgL/min/m^2$); $\rho_{3,4}$: Pearson correlation coefficient between DBP and SBP; $\rho_{1,2}$: Pearson correlation coefficient between CI and MAP; M: males; F: females.

3.2 Correlation between DBP and SBP

Diastolic and systolic blood pressure show a high degree of correlation: in the Framingham study a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.7-0.8 was reported for a sample of 2283 men and 2844 women, aged 30 to 62 (6). Another study reported that $\rho_{3,4} \geq 0.5$ in 95% of 140 subjects, with a mean value of 0.74 (7). In a sample of 24 healthy individuals (4), I calculated a correlation coefficient $\rho_{3,4} = 0.79$ with a p value $< 10^{-5}$ and 95%CI equal to [0.56, 0.90]. In another dataset of 26 healthy individuals

(5), I found $\rho_{3,4} = 0.63$, with $p = 0.0007$ and $95\%CI = [0.31, 0.82]$. If we pool these last two datasets, we find $\rho_{3,4} = 0.70$, with $p < 10^{-7}$ and $95\%CI = [0.52, 0.82]$ (Table 1, Table 2).

3.3 Correlation between CI and MAP

As for the correlation between CI and MAP, my search for a large dataset of healthy individuals has been without success. A study of 16 healthy subjects reports a small positive correlation between CO and MAP (8). By considering a small dataset previously mentioned (4), I found $\rho_{1,2} = 0.47$, $p = 0.02$, $95\%CI = [0.082, 0.73]$, while another dataset (5) suggests that the hypothesis that CI and MAP are independent cannot be rejected. If we pool these two datasets, we obtain $\rho_{1,2} = 0.30$, $p = 0.04$, $95\%CI = [0.013, 0.54]$ (Table 2). In a study including 783 critically ill patients admitted to the intensive care unit, CI and MAP were not correlated, eTable2 of (9).

Figure 1. Distribution of the CPI for 50 healthy subjects from (4), and (5), compared with normal, gamma, lognormal, and three-parameter lognormal densities with the same mean and standard deviation of the empirical distribution.

CI	DBP	SBP	MAP	CPI	size	Ref
0.001	0.56	0.0086	0.077	0.00078	24	(4)
0.015	0.42	0.22	0.35	0.02	26	(5)
0.00016	0.43	0.29	0.26	2.6e-05	50	pool

Table 3. For each dataset, the p value of the Shapiro-Wilk test is reported for the experimental distributions of cardiac index (CI), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), systolic blood pressure (SBP), mean arterial pressure (MAP), and cardiac power index.

3.4 Distribution of CPI

I have not found a clear answer to the question about the nature of the probability density of CPI, in the scientific literature. Nevertheless, if we consider the two small datasets previously mentioned, which include a total of 50 healthy subjects, the Shapiro-Wilk test rejects the null hypothesis of a normal distribution ($p = 2.64 \times 10^{-5}$) (Table 3), while the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test does not allow to reject the null hypothesis of gamma, lognormal, and three-parameter lognormal densities with the

same expectation and variance as the experimental data (Figure 1, Table 4), with the latter showing the best fit (the highest p value). In the case of a three-parameter lognormal density, a third condition was necessary to define the third parameter (see par. 6), and the median of the experimental data was imposed on the density.

normal	gamma	lognormal	three-parameter lognormal	size	Ref
0.061	0.23	0.37	0.52	24	(4)
0.866	0.99	1	-	26	(5)
0.047	0.23	0.41	0.49	50	pool

Table 4. For each dataset, the p value of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is reported for the distribution of CPI, for three different densities: normal, gamma, lognormal, and three-parameter lognormal. The parameters of the densities are determined so that their expectations and variances are the same as those of the experimental data.

normal	gamma	lognormal	three-parameter lognormal	size	Ref
0.93	0.98	0.99	0.99	24	(4)
0.52	0.58	0.61	-	26	(5)
0.40	0.52	0.57	0.64	50	pool

Table 5. Same as Table 4, but for MAP.

normal	gamma	lognormal	three-parameter lognormal	size	Ref
0.14	0.36	0.51	0.61	24	(4)
0.60	0.81	0.88	0.99	26	(5)
0.09	0.31	0.49	0.79	50	pool

Table 6. Same as Table 4, but for CI.

3.5 Calculation of the correlations from metadata

By considering the experimental data $\mu_1, \mu_3, \mu_4, \sigma_1, \sigma_3, \sigma_4$ and the hypotheses in Eq. 5, we can define the density of $CPI = CI \times MAP$ as a function of $\varrho_{1,2}$ and $\varrho_{3,4}$, by means of Eq. 20. For each point $(\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4})$, we can define the lognormal density $LogN(\mu, \sigma^2)$, with μ, σ given by Eq. 13. If we indicate the former density with $f_Y(y)$ and the latter with $f_{LN}(y)$, we can also calculate the integral

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad \Delta f = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f_Y(y) - f_{LN}(y)| dy$$

as a measure of the difference between f_Y and f_{LN} . Note that Δf is a function of $\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4}$ too, and its lowest value identifies the point $(\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4})$ for which f_Y is best approximated by a lognormal law with the same expectation and variance. In other words, with this method, I propose to use the point for which Δf reaches its minimum, as the values of the unknown correlations $\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4}$. The

application of this method is performed by the Octave script discussed in detail in the following paragraphs.

Figure 2. Plot of Δf as a function of $\rho_{1,2}, \rho_{3,4}$ for the data of the pooled sample of Table 2 and an auxiliary lognormal density.

CPI	$\rho_{3,4}$	$\rho_{1,2}$	fit	my method	Density
346.56 (125.60)	0.69	0.30	-	-	experimental
343.35 (107.24)	0	0	$\mu = 346.56$ $\sigma = 125.60$	$\mu = 343.35$ $\sigma = 107.24$	$N(\mu, \sigma^2)$
352.63 (136.71)	0.8	0.8	$\alpha = 7.61$ $\lambda = 0.022$	$\alpha = 6.65$ $\lambda = 0.019$	$\Gamma(\alpha, \lambda)$
348.65 (126.09)	0.8	0.46	$\mu = 5.79$ $\sigma = 0.351$	$\mu = 5.79$ $\sigma = 0.351$	$LogN(\mu, \sigma^2)$
346.44 (119.84)	0.8	0.27	$\mu = 5.657$ $\sigma = 0.391$ $b = 37.37$	$\mu = 7.074$ $\sigma = 0.101$ $b = -839$	$LogN(\mu, \sigma^2, b)$

Table 7. Results of the script for $\rho_{1,2}, \rho_{3,4} \in [0,0.8]$ and for 2000 extractions for the Montecarlo method. The script is applied to the pooled sample.

If we run the script with the experimental data from the pooled sample (Table 2), we obtain for CPI the results collected in Table 7. Note that there is a good agreement for mean and standard deviation of CPI between the values calculated by the method here discussed, and the experimental ones; as a consequence, the lognormal density identified by the method is almost identical to the one that fits the experimental data. Less good are the results for the two correlations, also because

the algorithm always picks the highest value for $\varrho_{3,4}$, and we have $\varrho_{3,4} = 0.8$ only because that is the upper limit I set for the correlation coefficients. The dependence of Δf to $\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4}$ can be seen in Figure 1.

The script performs the same analysis for normal, gamma, lognormal, and three-parameter lognormal density, but the results for normal and gamma are worse than what is obtained for lognormal (Table 7), while the three-parameter lognormal selection gives the best results for the mean and the correlations.

We now discuss in detail the script that performs the analysis. The complete code is reported in par. 6.5.

3.5.1 Moments and median

To calculate the density f_{LN} for a given point $\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4}$ we need the moments $E[Y], Var[Y]$, and to calculate the moments, we need μ_2, σ_2 . The following function performs these calculations, using Eq. 18, Eq. 19, and Eq. 6, respectively.

```
function [EY,VY,m2,s2] = mean_Y (m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r12,r34)
m2=((2*m3)+m4)/3;
s2=sqrt(4*s3^2 + s4^2 + 4*r34*s3*s4)/3;
EY=r12*s1*s2+m1*m2;
VY=(s2*m1)^2 + (s1*m2)^2 +(s1*s2)^2 + 2*r12*s1*s2*m1*m2 + (r12*s1*s2)^2;
endfunction
```

We also need the median, which is calculated according to Eq. 14 by the following function:

```
function [my] = median_Y (y,fY)
i=4;
int=0;
while (int<0.5)
int=trapz(y(1:i),fY(1:i));
i=i+1;
endwhile
my=y(i-1)
endfunction
```

From the median and the moments, we can calculate b . Instead of using the analytic approximation in Eq. 13, I perform a numerical solution of Eq. 15, using the approximated formula as the initial guess. The function that executes this task is the following.

```
function [b,b0] = solve_b (EY,VY,my)
b0 = my - 0.5*VY/(EY-my);
b = fsolve(@(b)((my-b)^2)*(VY + (EY-b)^2) - (EY-b)^4,b0);
endfunction
```

3.5.2 Density of the product of two Gaussian random variables

As discussed in par. 6.3, the density of CPI as a product of two Gaussian random variables does not have a simple expression, in the general case. There is indeed a series expansion that has been found in 2016 for it (10), but after several attempts, I decided to calculate Eq. 20 by numerical integration instead (Montecarlo method). To do so, the first step is to write a function for the integrand:

```
function integrand = func(y,s,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12)
```

```

A=-1/(2*(1-r12^2));
B1=(s-m1)/s1;
B2=(y-s*m2)/(s*s2);
B=(B1^2)-2*r12*B1*B2+(B2^2);
C=2*pi*s1*s2*sqrt(1-r12^2);
integrand=exp(A*B)/(C*abs(s));
endfunction

```

We then need the subroutine that performs the integration. But the integration is in $[-\infty, \infty]$, therefore we must find a finite interval as a surrogate for the infinite one. One way to do so is to search for an interval $[s_{min}, s_{max}]$ with $s_{min} < 0, s_{max} > 0$, such that the integrand is below a given cut-off (10^{-10} for instance) in both these values². We can then integrate in $[s_{min}, s_{max}]$, by considering that for the law of big numbers (11) we have

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(S_i) \xrightarrow{P} \int_{s_{min}}^{s_{max}} f(s) ds$$

where S is a random variable with uniform distribution in $[s_{min}, s_{max}]$. All that said, the subroutine that performs the numeric integration and gives as output f_Y for the point y specified in the arguments, is as follows:

```

function fY = density_Y(y,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12)
%
% search for suitable extremes of integration smin and smax
%
cut=10^(-10);
smin=-10;
smax=10;
integrand=1; % search for smin
while(integrand>cut)
    integrand = func(y,smin,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12);
    smin=smin-1;
endwhile
integrand=1; % search for smax
while(integrand>cut)
    integrand = func(y,smax,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12);
    smax=smax+1;
endwhile
%
% build the uniform random variable in [smin,smax]
%
steps=2000;
s(1)=smin;
s(steps)=smax;
ds=(smax-smin)/(steps-1);
s=s(1):ds:s(steps);
%
% Montecarlo method of integration
%
fY=0;
for i=1:steps
    integrand = func(y,s(i),m1,m2,s1,s2,r12);
    fY=fY+integrand;
endfor

```

² Note that we are justified in doing so because the integrand tends to zero for $|s| \rightarrow \infty$, whatever the value of y .

```
fY=((smax-smin)/steps)*fY;
endfunction
```

3.5.3 The auxiliary density

To find $\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4}$ we need a condition to impose to f_Y . We can for instance ask that f_Y overlaps with a three-parameter lognormal density with the same mean, variance, and median. The same applies to normal, gamma, and classic lognormal density. In other words, we need an auxiliary density to use as a constraint for the determination of the correlations. Note that what is seen in par. 3 suggests that the best choice is one of the following: gamma, lognormal, or three-parameter lognormal. As mentioned before, we will search for the point $\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4}$ in which we have the lowest value for Δf (Eq. 7). To calculate the array of the density of choice, which will be indicated f_{eY} , we use the following function. Note that select is 1 for the normal density, 2 for the gamma, 3 for the lognormal, and 4 for the three-parameter lognormal.

```
function feY = e_density_Y (y,EY,VY,b,select)
switch (select)
case {1} % normal density
    feY=normpdf(y,EY,sqrt(VY));
case {2} % gamma density
    alpha=(EY^2)/VY;
    lambda=EY/VY;
    shape=alpha;
    scale=1/lambda;
    feY=gampdf(y,shape,scale);
case {3} % lognormal
    MU=log((EY^2)/sqrt(VY+EY^2));
    SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EY^2));
    feY=lognpdf(y,MU,SIGMA);
case {4} % three-parameter lognormal
    if ((y-b)<=0)
        feY=0;
    else
        EYb=EY-b;
        MU=log((EYb^2)/sqrt(VY+EYb^2));
        SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EYb^2));
        A=-0.5*((log(y-b)-MU)/SIGMA)^2;
        C=1/(SIGMA*(y-b)*sqrt(2*pi));
        feY=C*exp(A);
    endif
endswitch
endfunction
```

3.5.4 Main program

The task of the main program is to calculate Δf (Eq. 7) and find the point $\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4}$ for which it reaches its minimum. It also plots the surface $\Delta f(\varrho_{1,2}, \varrho_{3,4})$. Coding in this case is straightforward.

```
f=0;
for select=1:4;
%
% a string for the output
%
switch (select)
```

```

case {1} % normal density
    stringa = 'N(E[Y],Var[Y])';
case {2} % gamma density
    stringa = '{\Gamma}({\alpha},{\lambda})';
case {3} % lognormal
    stringa = 'LogN(E[Y],Var[Y])';
case {4} % three-parameter lognormal
    stringa = '3pLogN(E[Y],Var[Y],b)';
endswitch
%
% calculating score
%
for i=1:length(r)
    for h=1:length(r)
        [EY,VY,m2,s2] = mean_Y (m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r(i),r(h))
        y(1)=EY-4*sqrt(VY);
        y(steps)=EY+4*sqrt(VY);
        dy=(y(steps)-y(1))/(steps-1);
        y=y(1):dy:y(steps);
        %
        for j=1:length(y) % find fY
            fY(j) = density_Y (y(j),m1,m2,s1,s2,r(i));
        endfor
        %
        [my] = median_Y (y,fY) % median of fY
        if (select==4)
            [b,b0] = solve_b (EY,VY,my);
        else
            b=0;
        endif
        %
        for j=1:length(y) % find feY
            feY(j) = e_density_Y (y(j),EY,VY,b,select);
            delta_f(j) = abs(fY(j)-feY(j));
        endfor
        score(i,h)=trapz(y,delta_f); % area between fY, feY
    endfor
endfor
%
% plot score
%
f=f+1;
figure(f)
surf(r,r,score)
xlabel('r_{3,4}','FontSize',15)
ylabel('r_{1,2}','FontSize',15)
title(strcat("\Delta f, ",stringa),"fontsize",15)
%
% search for the best and worst normal approximation
%
min_score=score(1,1);
i_min=1;
h_min=1;
max_score=score(1,1);
i_max=1;
h_max=1;
for i=1:length(r)

```

```

for h=1:length(r)
  if (score(i,h)<min_score)
    min_score=score(i,h);
    i_min=i;
    h_min=h;
  endif
  if (score(i,h)>max_score)
    max_score=score(i,h);
    i_max=i;
    h_max=h;
  endif
endfor
endfor
%
Deltaf_best(select)=score(i_min,h_min);
%
% plot the best approximation
%
i=i_min;
h=h_min;
f=f+1;
plotting(i,h,m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r,score,f,select,stringa,steps,name{data_i})
endfor

```

3.5.5 Subroutine for plotting and output

This subroutine generates the plot for the auxiliary density and f_Y in correspondence with the point $Q_{1,2}, Q_{3,4}$ for which Δf reaches its lowest value (best fit). It also writes on the screen the values for $Q_{1,2}, Q_{3,4}, E[Y], Var[Y], m_y$ and the parameters of the auxiliary density.

```

function plotting(i,h,m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r,score,f,select,stringa,steps,name)
[EY,VY,m2,s2] = mean_Y (m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r(i),r(h));
y(1)=EY-4*sqrt(VY);
y(steps)=EY+4*sqrt(VY);
dy=(y(steps)-y(1))/(steps-1);
y=y(1):dy:y(steps);
%
for j=1:length(y)
  fY(j) = density_Y (y(j),m1,m2,s1,s2,r(i));
endfor
%
[my] = median_Y (y,fY);
if (select==4)
  [b,b0] = solve_b (EY,VY,my);
else
  b=0;
endif
%
for j=1:length(y)
  feY(j) = e_density_Y (y(j),EY,VY,b,select);
endfor
figure(f)
plot(y,fY,'-k','Linewidth',1)
hold on
plot(y,feY,'-r','Linewidth',1)
xlabel('Y','FontSize',15)

```

```

ylabel('probability density','FontSize',15)
legend('f_{Y}',stringa,'FontSize',15)
str0='{rho_{1,2}}=';
str1='{rho_{3,4}}=';
str2='{mu_{Y}}=';
str3='{SD(Y)}=';
str4=strcat('{\mu_{1}}=',num2str(m1));
str5=strcat('{\mu_{2}}=',num2str(m2));
str6=strcat('{\sigma_{1}}=',num2str(s1));
str7=strcat('{\sigma_{2}}=',num2str(s2));
str8=' score=';
str00=num2str(r(i));
str11=num2str(r(h));
str22=num2str(EY);
str33=num2str(sqrt(VY));
str88=num2str(score(i,h));
title(strcat(str0,str00,str1,str11,str2,str22,str3,str33,str4,str5,str6,str7,str8,str88),'FontSize',15)
grid on
grid minor
%
% write the parameters for the exact density
%
switch (select)
case {1} % normal density
    str_output="Parameters of the best normal fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY
    SD=sqrt(VY)
    my
    disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r(i))))
    disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r(h))))
    mu=EY
    sigma=sqrt(VY)
case {2} % gamma density
    str_output="Parameters of the best gamma fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY
    SD=sqrt(VY)
    my
    disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r(i))))
    disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r(h))))
    alpha=(EY^2)/VY
    lambda=EY/VY
case {3} % lognormal
    str_output="Parameters of the best lognormal fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY
    SD=sqrt(VY)
    my
    disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r(i))))
    disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r(h))))
    MU=log((EY^2)/sqrt(VY+EY^2))
    SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EY^2))
case {4} % three-parameter lognormal
    str_output="Parameters of the best three-parameter lognormal fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY

```

```

SD=sqrt(VY)
my
disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r(i))))
disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r(h))))
b
EYb=EY-b;
MU=log((EYb^2)/sqrt(VY+EYb^2))
SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EYb^2))
endswitch
endfunction

```

3.6 Note on the correlation between DBP and SBP

We assume for $\rho_{1,2}, \rho_{3,4}$ the values within the corresponding 95CIs for the pooled sample in Table 2, we then calculate the mean and variance of CPI from Eq. 18, Eq. 19, and Eq. 14 respectively. We can then derive a lognormal density for CPI by calculating parameters μ, σ from Eq. 13. If we want to derive a three-parameter lognormal density, we must calculate the median of the density in Eq. 20. In Figure 3, the expectation and the standard deviation for the values of the parameters $\mu_1, \mu_3, \mu_4, \sigma_1, \sigma_3, \sigma_4$ for the pooled sample (Table 2), as a function of the correlations for $\rho_{1,2} \in [0.01, 0.54]$ and $\rho_{3,4} \in [0.51, 0.82]$. It can be noted how little influence the correlation between DBP and SBP ($\rho_{3,4}$) has on the two moments of f_Y . Therefore, we can assign a fixed value to $\rho_{3,4}$ (0.75, for instance).

Figure 3. Expectation (Eq. 18) and standard deviation (Eq. 19) for the values of the parameters $\mu_1, \mu_3, \mu_4, \sigma_1, \sigma_3, \sigma_4$ of the pooled sample (Table 2).

If we decide to use a gamma density for CPI, we can calculate α, λ with Eq. 17, while if we decide on a lognormal density, we use Eq. 13 for μ, σ . In the case of the three-parameter lognormal distribution, we need to calculate m_y from the density in Eq. 16. In either case, we obtain a density that is completely defined once we assign $\rho_{1,2}$. We can variate $\rho_{1,2}$ in $[0.01, 0.54]$ and see how the density varies correspondingly.

4 Application to data about ME/CFS

We now apply the method here discussed to metadata collected during a normal tilt table test performed on both normal subjects and ME/CFS patients (Table 8). The duration of the orthostatic stress at 70 degrees was 25-30 minutes. Measures were taken at baseline (supine position), during the test, and at the end of the tilt (12). Note that while in the sample that we used to study the density of

CPI (par. 3.4) the measure of CO was performed by direct Fick method, in the present samples the acquisition of CO was obtained by suprasternal aortic Doppler imaging. While the former is a method based on the analysis of gas exchange through the mouth, the latter uses ecographic techniques to measure SV. Moreover, while the sample used to study the density of CPI was composed mainly of males, most of the subjects in the ME/CFS group and the control group were females.

I run the numeric method with the following parameters: $\varrho_{1,2} \in [0.01, 0.54]$, $\varrho_{3,4} \in [0.7, 0.8]$, numeric integration for Eq. 20 by the Montecarlo method with 2000 extractions. I then used the Student's t-test to compare the means of CPI between patients and controls, in both supine and end-tilt positions. The results are collected in Table 9 and show a significant increase in CPI among ME/CFS patients, in a supine position.

Hematological parameters		HC (37)	ME/CFS (150)
supine DBP (mmHg)	DBP_1	77 (6)	79 (9)
supine SBP (mmHg)	SBP_1	130 (12)	136 (18)
supine CI (L/min/m ²)	CI_1	2.28 (0.37)	2.38 (0.36)
end-tilt DBP (mmHg)	DBP_2	81 (7)	86 (10)
end-tilt SBP (mmHg)	SBP_2	126 (13)	133 (18)
end tilt CI (L/min/m ²)	CI_2	2.05 (0.28)	1.90 (0.34)

Table 8. Means and standard deviations for DBP, SBP, and CI, in both supine and tilted positions, for 362 ME/CFS patients and 52 controls. From (12).

It should be noted that the Student's t-test may not be appropriate in this setting, since the density of CPI is a three-parameter lognormal one for both groups. Therefore, a parametric test for this kind of density should be developed. I found such a parametric test for the case of a two-parameter lognormal, i.e. when $b = 0$ (13). But it cannot be directly applied to the case we are interested in, to my understanding, unless we assume that b is the same for patients and controls. The two three-parametr lognormal densities for CPI in HC and ME/CFS obtained by my method, are plotted in Figure 4.

CPI	$\varrho_{3,4}$	$\varrho_{1,2}$	$LogN(\mu, \sigma^2, b)$	sample	t-test
216 (40)	0.8	0.06	$\mu = 6.5, \sigma = 0.06, b = -450$	HC supine	0.043
234 (50)	0.7	0.3	$\mu = 6.2, \sigma = 0.10, b = -262$	ME/CFS supine	
196 (32)	0.7	0.01	$\mu = 6.3, \sigma = 0.06, b = -334$	HC end-tilt	0.7
193 (45)	0.8	0.19	$\mu = 6.1, \sigma = 0.10, b = -251$	ME/CFS end-tilt	

Table 9. Output of the method here discussed, for metadata in Table 9. From left to right: mean and standard deviation for CPI, correlation coefficients, parameters of the three-parameter lognormal density, name of the sample, and t-test for the comparison of the means of CPI in healthy controls and ME/CFS patients in both supine and end-tilt position. CPI: cardiac power index (mmHgL/min/m²); $\varrho_{3,4}$: Pearson correlation coefficient between DBP and SBP; $\varrho_{1,2}$: Pearson correlation coefficient between CI and MAP.

Figure 4. Probability densities of CPI for healthy controls (dashed line) and ME/CFS patients (continue line) in a supine position. The distributions are obtained from three-parameter lognormal densities, with the parameters collected in Table 9.

5 Application to data about POTS

I considered data from a tilt table testing on 16 healthy subjects and 32 individuals with a previous diagnosis of postural-orthostatic tachycardia syndrome (POTS), a condition characterized by an increase of HR of more than 30 bpm during a 10-minute standing test, in the presence of normal blood pressure (14). The POTS group presented normal CO in a supine position. The tilt lasted 10 minutes at 70° and before and during the experiment, several hemodynamic parameters were evaluated; CO and MAP among them (Table 10). The table was built from the information presented in the diagrams of Figure 2 of (14) by magnification and printing of the picture; I then used a rule and simple calculations to measure the values from the figure.

CO (L/min)	MAP (mmHg)	sample	size
5.08 (0.38)	87.5 (2.5)	HC end-tilt	16
2.91 (0.30)	90 (3.5)	POTS end-tilt	32

Table 10. Cardiac output (CO) and mean arterial pressure (MAP) at the end of a 10-minute orthostatic stress at 70 degrees. A group of 32 POTS patients with normal supine CO and a control of 16 healthy individuals were considered. From (14).

In the pooled sample used for the study of the distribution of CPI in par. 3.4, the correlation ρ between CO and MAP is 0.37 with a 95%CI of [0.09, 0.59]. We can calculate $E[CP]$ and $Var[CP]$ from Eq. 18, Eq. 19 respectively, as a function of ρ , for both the control group and the POTS group. We can then calculate the p value of the Student's t-test for the comparison of the means of CP, as ρ varies in [0.09, 0.59] independently for the two groups. The highest p value that we obtain is $p = 1.28 \cdot 10^{-20}$, therefore we can conclude that CI is lower in POTS patients than in controls, at the end of the tilt, despite a normal MAP among patients. This means that, at least in some cases, POTS represents a strategy for keeping normal blood pressure with a lower mechanical energy expenditure by the left ventricle. The R script that performs all the t-tets is the following one.

```

# file name: t_test_POTS
#
# Rome 1/10/2023
#
r<-seq(0.09,0.59,by=0.01)
#
# first value is for HC, second for POTS
#
n<-c(16,32) # sample size
nA<-n[1]
nB<-n[2]
m1<-c(5.08,2.91) # mean of CO
s1<-c(0.38,0.30) # sd of CO
m2<-c(87.5,90) # mean of MAP
s2<-c(2.5,3.5) # sd of MAP
#
moments<-function(m1,m2,s1,s2,r){
  EY<-r*s1*s2+m1*m2
  VY<-(s2*m1)^2 + (s1*m2)^2 + (s1*s2)^2 + 2*r*s1*s2*m1*m2 + (r*s1*s2)^2
  SDY<-sqrt(VY)
  return(c(EY,SDY))
}
p<-matrix(nrow=length(r),ncol=length(r))
for (i in 1:length(r)) {
  for (j in 1:length(r)) {
    temp<-moments(m1[1],m2[1],s1[1],s2[1],r[i]) # controls
    mA<-temp[1]
    sA<-temp[2]
    temp<-moments(m1[2],m2[2],s1[2],s2[2],r[j]) # patients
    mB<-temp[1]
    sB<-temp[2]
    #
    sp<-sqrt(((nA-1)*sA^2 + (nB-1)*sB^2)/(nA+nB-2))
    TS<-abs(mA-mB)/(sp*sqrt(1/nA + 1/nB))
    p[i,j]<-2*pt(-TS,df=nA+nB-2,lower.tail = TRUE, log.p = FALSE)
  }
}
p_max<-max(p)

```

One might expect that when there is an increase in HR, there is a reduction in SV because there is less time for the left ventricle to fill. This is the case, and if we perform a linear regression between HR and SVI on 52 healthy subjects in a supine position we find

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad HR = -0.9769 \cdot SVI + 99.18 \Rightarrow SVI = -\frac{HR-99.18}{0.9769}$$

where SVI is expressed in ml/m^2 . After 25 minutes of tilt at 70 degrees, the regression law becomes

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad HR = -1.968 \cdot SVI + 130.7 \Rightarrow SVI = -\frac{HR-130.7}{1.968}$$

These linear regressions are taken from (15). Therefore, for CPI at the end of tilt testing, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad CPI = CI \times MAP = SVI \times HR \times MAP = -\frac{HR-130.7}{1.968} \times HR \times MAP$$

If we plot CPI as a function of HR, for the values of MAP in Table 10, we have Figure 5 where CPI decreases as HR increases. Therefore, increasing HR can be considered also a strategy for maintaining MAP at a constant level, but at a lower mechanical power expenditure by the left ventricle. Note that Eq. 11 has been calculated from data on healthy individuals at the end of a tilt test, and since healthy individuals do not show a substantial increase in heart rate as POTS patients do, this model might be wrong for the higher values of the abscissa.

Figure 5. CPI (watt/m²) as a function of HR (beats/minute) for two values of MAP, for end-tilt, according to Eq. 11, multiplied by the conversion factor in Eq. 4.

The script that generates Figure 5 is the following one.

```
% file name = CPI_POTS
% date of creation = 2/10/2023
clear all
close all
%
K=2.21*1e-06; % conversion from mmHgxml/min to watt
%
HR=[70:1:135];
MAP=[85,90,95];
for j=1:3
    for i=1:length(HR)
        CPI(j,i)=(-(HR(i)-130.7)/1.968)*HR(i)*MAP(j);
    endfor
endfor
CPI=CPI*K;
%
plot(HR,CPI(1,:),'-k','Linewidth', 1) % Healthy subjects
hold on
plot(HR,CPI(2,:),'--k','Linewidth', 1) % POTS
hold on
plot(HR,CPI(3,:),'-k','Linewidth', 1) % POTS
legend('MAP=85 mmHg','MAP=90 mmHg','MAP=95 mmHg','location','northeast','fontsize',15)
```

```
xlabel('HR (beats/min)', 'fontsize', 15)
ylabel('CPI (watt/m^2)', 'fontsize', 15)
grid on
grid minor
axis([70, 130, 0.1, 0.5])
```

6 Appendix

6.1 Three-parameter lognormal density

Given the r.v. $X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$, we define the 3-parameter lognormal random variable $Y = b + e^X$. Its density is

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad f_Y(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma(y-b)} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\ln(y-b)-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}$$

for $y > b$, it is zero otherwise. It is possible to show that

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad b \cong m_y - \frac{\text{Var}[Y]}{2(E[Y]-m_y)}, \quad \mu = \ln \frac{(E[Y]-b)^2}{\sqrt{\text{Var}[Y] + (E[Y]-b)^2}}, \quad \sigma^2 = \ln \left(\frac{\text{Var}[Y]}{(E[Y]-b)^2} + 1 \right)$$

where m_y is the median of Y , defined by

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \int_b^{m_y} f_Y(y) dy = \frac{1}{2}$$

The three-parameter lognormal density can be indicated $\text{Log}N(\mu, \sigma^2, b)$ and for $b = 0$ it gives the ordinary lognormal density of parameters μ, σ , for which we use the notation $\text{Log}N(\mu, \sigma^2)$. The formula for b is an approximation proposed in (16) and it is acceptable only for small values of σ^2 . The exact value of b is the real solution (with multiplicity 2) of the equation

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad (m_y - b)^2 [\text{Var}[Y] + (E[Y] - b)^2] - (E[Y] - b)^4 = 0$$

For more details on how to derive these formulae, see (17).

6.2 Gamma density

We define a gamma distribution of parameters α (shape), λ (rate) the probability density described by the function

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad f(y) = \frac{\lambda^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} y^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda y}$$

for $y > 0$, and that assumes the value zero otherwise. We indicate it with the symbol $\Gamma(\alpha, \lambda)$. Parameters α, λ can be derived from the expectation and the variance:

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad \alpha = \frac{E^2[X]}{\text{Var}[X]}, \quad \lambda = \frac{E[X]}{\text{Var}[X]}$$

6.3 Product of two correlated normal random variables

Given $X_1 = N(\mu_1, \sigma_1^2), X_2 = N(\mu_2, \sigma_2^2)$ and $Y = X_1, X_2$, from the definition of the Pearson correlation coefficient we have

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad E[Y] = \varrho_{1,2}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + \mu_1\mu_2$$

where $\varrho_{1,2}$ is the correlation coefficient between X_1, X_2 . Moreover, it has been demonstrated (18) that

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad \text{Var}[Y] = \sigma_2^2\mu_1^2 + \sigma_1^2\mu_2^2 + \sigma_1^2\sigma_2^2 + 2\varrho_{1,2}\sigma_1\sigma_2\mu_1\mu_2 + \varrho_{1,2}^2\sigma_1^2\sigma_2^2$$

It can be shown – as detailed in (19) – that

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad f_Y(y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_1\sigma_2\sqrt{1-\varrho_{1,2}^2}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-\frac{1}{2(1-\varrho_{1,2}^2)}\left[\left(\frac{s-\mu_1}{\sigma_1}\right)^2 - 2\varrho\left(\frac{s-\mu_1}{\sigma_1}\right)\left(\frac{y-s\mu_2}{s\sigma_2}\right) + \left(\frac{y-s\mu_2}{s\sigma_2}\right)^2\right]}}{|s|} ds$$

Recently, it has been demonstrated that this integral can be expressed as an infinite series of modified Bessel functions of the second type whose first 30 addends provide a reasonable approximation for most of the applications (10). I made several attempts with the series expansion, but I obtained the best results with numerical integration of Eq. 20 by the Montecarlo method. So I decided not to use the expansion in the present work.

6.4 Script for the statistical analyses

This R script generates the tables and diagram of par. 3. It also generates supplementary output not shown in this document.

```
# file name: Pooled
#
# Rome 17/09/2023
#
library(EnvStats) # we need this for dlnorm3
#
# Read data
#
datalist<-list()
datalist[[1]]<-read.csv("Stead 1945.csv",sep=";")
datalist[[2]]<-read.csv("Barratt-Boyes 1958.csv",sep=";")
#
# We generate a pooled dataset
#
datalist[[3]]<-rbind(datalist[[1]],datalist[[2]])
#
# I set a data.frame in which I'll put the results for means, SDs, and CCs
#
papers<-c("Stead 1945","Barratt-Boyes 1958","pooled")
column_names<-c("CO","BSA","CI","DBP","SBP","MAP","CPI","r3,4","r1,2","size","Ref")
output<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=length(papers),ncol=length(column_names)))
colnames(output)<-column_names
output$Ref<-papers
#
# I set a data.frame in which I'll put the p values for the Shapiro_Wilk
# Normality Tests
#
column_names<-c("CO","BSA","CI","DBP","SBP","MAP","CPI","size","Ref")
Shapiro_Wilk<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=length(papers),ncol=length(column_names)))
```

```

colnames(Shapiro_Wilk)<-column_names
Shapiro_Wilk$Ref<-papers
#
# I set a data.frame in which I'll put the p values for the Kolmogorov test for CPI
#
column_names<-c("normal","gamma","lognormal","t_p_lognormal","Ref")
Kolmogorov_CPI<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=length(papers),ncol=length(column_names)))
colnames(Kolmogorov_CPI)<-column_names
Kolmogorov_CPI$Ref<-papers
#
# I set a data.frame in which I'll put the p values for the Kolmogorov test for CI
#
column_names<-c("normal","gamma","lognormal","t_p_lognormal","Ref")
Kolmogorov_CI<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=length(papers),ncol=length(column_names)))
colnames(Kolmogorov_CI)<-column_names
Kolmogorov_CI$Ref<-papers
#
# I set a data.frame in which I'll put the p values for the Kolmogorov test for MAP
#
column_names<-c("normal","gamma","lognormal","t_p_lognormal","Ref")
Kolmogorov_MAP<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=length(papers),ncol=length(column_names)))
colnames(Kolmogorov_MAP)<-column_names
Kolmogorov_MAP$Ref<-papers
#
for (k in 1:length(datalist)) {
  mydata<-datalist[[k]]
  output$size[k]<-length(mydata$CI)
  MAP<-mydata$DBP+(mydata$SBP-mydata$DBP)/3
  CPI<-mydata$CI*MAP
  #
  # Create the scatterplot with regression line
  #
  LR<-lm(mydata$CI~MAP)
  summary(LR)
  string<-paste("CI vs MAP, ",papers[[k]])
  plot(MAP,mydata$CI,pch=19,col="blue",main=string,xlab="MAP (mmHg)",ylab="CI (L/min)")
  abline(LR,col="red")
  #
  # Calculate means and SDs
  #
  str1<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),mean(mydata$CO,na.rm=T))
  str2<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),sd(mydata$CO,na.rm=T))
  str3<-paste(str1,"(",str2,")")
  output$CO[k]<-str3
  #
  str1<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),mean(mydata$BSA,na.rm=T))
  str2<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),sd(mydata$BSA,na.rm=T))
  str3<-paste(str1,"(",str2,")")
  output$BSA[k]<-str3
  #
  str1<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),mean(mydata$CI,na.rm=T))
  str2<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),sd(mydata$CI,na.rm=T))
  str3<-paste(str1,"(",str2,")")
  output$CI[k]<-str3
  #
  str1<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),mean(mydata$DBP,na.rm=T))
  str2<-sprintf(paste("%.",2,"f",sep=""),sd(mydata$DBP,na.rm=T))

```

```

str3<-paste(str1,"(",str2,")")
output$DBP[k]<-str3
#
str1<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),mean(mydata$SBP,na.rm=T))
str2<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),sd(mydata$SBP,na.rm=T))
str3<-paste(str1,"(",str2,")")
output$SBP[k]<-str3
#
str1<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),mean(MAP,na.rm=T))
str2<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),sd(MAP,na.rm=T))
str3<-paste(str1,"(",str2,")")
output$MAP[k]<-str3
#
str1<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),mean(CPI,na.rm=T))
str2<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),sd(CPI,na.rm=T))
str3<-paste(str1,"(",str2,")")
output$CPI[k]<-str3
#
# Calculate the Pearson correlation coefficients
#
r<-cor.test(mydata$DBP,mydata$SBP,method=c("pearson"))
if (r$p.value<0.05) {
  str1<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),r$estimate)
  str2<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),r$conf.int[1])
  str3<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),r$conf.int[2])
  str4<-paste(str1,"[",str2,",",str3,"]")
  output$r3,4`[k]<-str4
}
r<-cor.test(mydata$CI,MAP,method=c("pearson"))
if (r$p.value<0.05) {
  str1<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),r$estimate)
  str2<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),r$conf.int[1])
  str3<-sprintf(paste("%. ",2,"f",sep=""),r$conf.int[2])
  str4<-paste(str1,"[",str2,",",str3,"]")
  output$r1,2`[k]<-str4
}
#
# Q-Q plots
#
qqnorm(mydata$CO,main=paste("Normal Q-Q Plot for CO",papers[k]))
qqline(mydata$CO,col=2)
qqnorm(mydata$BSA,main=paste("Normal Q-Q Plot for BSA",papers[k]))
qqline(mydata$BSA,col=2)
qqnorm(mydata$CI,main=paste("Normal Q-Q Plot for CI",papers[k]))
qqline(mydata$CI,col=2)
qqnorm(MAP,main=paste("Normal Q-Q Plot for MAP",papers[k]))
qqline(MAP,col=2)
qqnorm(mydata$DBP,main=paste("Normal Q-Q Plot for DBP",papers[k]))
qqline(mydata$DBP,col=2)
qqnorm(mydata$SBP,main=paste("Normal Q-Q Plot for SBP",papers[k]))
qqline(mydata$SBP,col=2)
qqnorm(CPI,main=paste("Normal Q-Q Plot for CPI",papers[k]))
qqline(CPI,col=2)
#
# Shapiro_Wilk Normality Test
#
Shapiro_Wilk$size[k]<-length(mydata$CO)

```

```

Shapiro_Wilkt<-shapiro.test(mydata$CO)
Shapiro_Wilk$CO[k]<-Shapiro_Wilkt$p.value
Shapiro_Wilkt<-shapiro.test(mydata$BSA)
Shapiro_Wilk$BSA[k]<-Shapiro_Wilkt$p.value
Shapiro_Wilkt<-shapiro.test(mydata$CI)
Shapiro_Wilk$CI[k]<-Shapiro_Wilkt$p.value
Shapiro_Wilkt<-shapiro.test(mydata$DBP)
Shapiro_Wilk$DBP[k]<-Shapiro_Wilkt$p.value
Shapiro_Wilkt<-shapiro.test(mydata$SBP)
Shapiro_Wilk$SBP[k]<-Shapiro_Wilkt$p.value
Shapiro_Wilkt<-shapiro.test(MAP)
Shapiro_Wilk$MAP[k]<-Shapiro_Wilkt$p.value
Shapiro_Wilkt<-shapiro.test(CPI)
Shapiro_Wilk$CPI[k]<-Shapiro_Wilkt$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of MAP for normal density
#
alpha<-c()
lambda<-c()
sigma<-c()
sigma2<-c()
mu<-c()
mu2<-c()
b<-c()
#
mMAP<-mean(MAP,na.rm=T)
VMAP<-var(MAP,na.rm=T)
KT<-ks.test(MAP,"pnorm",mean=mMAP,sd=sqrt(VMAP))
Kolmogorov_MAP$normal[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of MAP for gamma density
#
alpha[1]<-(mMAP^2)/VMAP
lambda[1]<-mMAP/VMAP
KT<-ks.test(MAP,"pgamma",shape=alpha[1],rate=lambda[1])
Kolmogorov_MAP$gamma[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of MAP for lognormal density
#
sigma[1]<-sqrt(log(1+VMAP/mMAP^2))
mu[1]<-log(mMAP^2/sqrt(VMAP+mMAP^2))
KT<-ks.test(MAP,"plnorm",meanlog=mu[1],sdlog=sigma[1])
Kolmogorov_MAP$lognormal[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of MAP for three-parameter lognormal density
#
medMAP<-median(MAP,na.rm=T)
mMAP<-mean(MAP,na.rm=T)
VMAP<-var(MAP,na.rm=T)
b[1]<-medMAP-0.5*VMAP/(mMAP-medMAP)
if (b[1]>0) {
  temp<-(mMAP-b[1])^2
  mu2[1]<-log(temp/sqrt(VMAP+temp))
  sigma2[1]<-sqrt(log(1+VMAP/temp))
  KT<-ks.test(MAP,"plnorm3",meanlog=mu2[1],sdlog=sigma2[1],threshold=b[1])
  Kolmogorov_MAP$t_p_lognormal[k]<-KT$p.value
}

```

```

if (b[1]<=0) Kolmogorov_MAP$t_p_lognormal[k]<-NA
#
# Kolmogorov test of CI for normal density
#
mCI<-mean(mydata$CI,na.rm=T)
VCI<-var(mydata$CI,na.rm=T)
KT<-ks.test(mydata$CI,"pnorm",mean=mCI,sd=sqrt(VCI))
Kolmogorov_CI$normal[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of CI for gamma density
#
alpha[2]<-(mCI^2)/VCI
lambda[2]<-mCI/VCI
KT<-ks.test(mydata$CI,"pgamma",shape=alpha[2],rate=lambda[2])
Kolmogorov_CI$gamma[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of CI for lognormal density
#
sigma[2]<-sqrt(log(1+VCI/mCI^2))
mu[2]<-log(mCI^2/sqrt(VCI+mCI^2))
KT<-ks.test(mydata$CI,"plnorm",meanlog=mu[2],sdlog=sigma[2])
Kolmogorov_CI$lognormal[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of CI for three-parameter lognormal density
#
medCI<-median(mydata$CI,na.rm=T)
mCI<-mean(mydata$CI,na.rm=T)
VCI<-var(mydata$CI,na.rm=T)
b[2]<-medCI-0.5*VCI/(mCI-medCI)
if (b[2]>0) {
  temp<-(mCI-b[2])^2
  mu2[2]<-log(temp/sqrt(VCI+temp))
  sigma2[2]<-sqrt(log(1+VCI/temp))
  KT<-ks.test(mydata$CI,"plnorm3",meanlog=mu2[2],sdlog=sigma2[2],threshold=b[2])
  Kolmogorov_CI$t_p_lognormal[k]<-KT$p.value
}
if (b[2]<=0) Kolmogorov_CI$t_p_lognormal[k]<-NA
#
# Kolmogorov test of CPI for normal density
#
mCPI<-mean(CPI,na.rm=T)
VCPI<-var(CPI,na.rm=T)
KT<-ks.test(CPI,"pnorm",mean=mCPI,sd=sqrt(VCPI))
Kolmogorov_CPI$normal[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of CPI for gamma density
#
alpha[3]<-(mCPI^2)/VCPI
lambda[3]<-mCPI/VCPI
KT<-ks.test(CPI,"pgamma",shape=alpha,rate=lambda)
Kolmogorov_CPI$gamma[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of CPI for lognormal density
#
sigma[3]<-sqrt(log(1+VCPI/mCPI^2))
mu[3]<-log(mCPI^2/sqrt(VCPI+mCPI^2))
KT<-ks.test(CPI,"plnorm",meanlog=mu,sdlog=sigma)

```

```

Kolmogorov_CPI$lognormal[k]<-KT$p.value
#
# Kolmogorov test of CPI for three-parameter lognormal density
#
medCPI<-median(CPI,na.rm=T)
mCPI<-mean(CPI,na.rm=T)
VCPI<-var(CPI,na.rm=T)
b[3]<-medCPI-0.5*VCPI/(mCPI-medCPI)
if (b[3]>0) {
  temp<-(mCPI-b[3])^2
  mu2[3]<-log(temp/sqrt(VCPI+temp))
  sigma2[3]<-sqrt(log(1+VCPI/temp))
  KT<-ks.test(CPI,"plnorm3",meanlog=mu2[3],sdlog=sigma2[3],threshold=b[3])
  Kolmogorov_CPI$t_p_lognormal[k]<-KT$p.value
}
#
# Plots for distributions
#
Lista<-list(mydata$DBP,mydata$SBP,MAP,mydata$CI,CPI)
label<-c("DBP","SBP","MAP","CI","CPI")
N<-10
bp<-c()
for (i in 1:(length(Lista))) {
  V<-Lista[[i]]
  bp[1]<-min(V,na.rm=T)
  bp[N]<-max(V,na.rm=T)
  delta<-(bp[N]-bp[1])/(N-1)
  for (j in 2:N) bp[j]<-bp[j-1]+delta
  x<-seq(bp[1],bp[N],by=0.01)
  if (i<3) {
    density=dnorm(x,mean=mean(V,na.rm=T),sd=sd(V,na.rm=T))
    hist(V,bp,probability=T,xlab=label[i],main=paste("Histogram of",label[i],papers[k]),
        xlim=c(bp[1],bp[N]),ylim=c(min(density),2*max(density)))
    par(new=T)
    plot(x,density,type="l",xlab="",ylab="",xlim=c(bp[1],bp[N]),
        ylim=c(min(density),2*max(density)))
  }
  if (i>=3) {
    density1=dnorm(x,mean=mean(V,na.rm=T),sd=sd(V,na.rm=T))
    density2=dgamma(x,shape=alpha[i-2],rate=lambda[i-2])
    density3=dlnorm(x,meanlog=mu[i-2],sdlog=sigma[i-2])
    density4=dlnorm3(x,meanlog=mu2[i-2],sdlog=sigma2[i-2],threshold=b[i-2])
    hist(V,bp,probability=T,xlab=label[i],main=paste("Histogram of",label[i],papers[k]),
        xlim=c(bp[1],bp[N]),ylim=c(min(density1),2*max(density1)))
    par(new=T)
    plot(x,density1,type="l",lty=1,lwd=2,xlab="",ylab="",xlim=c(bp[1],bp[N]),
        ylim=c(min(density1),2*max(density1)))
    par(new=T)
    plot(x,density2,type="l",lty=2,lwd=2,xlab="",ylab="",xlim=c(bp[1],bp[N]),
        ylim=c(min(density1),2*max(density1)))
    par(new=T)
    plot(x,density3,type="l",lty=3,lwd=2,xlab="",ylab="",xlim=c(bp[1],bp[N]),
        ylim=c(min(density1),2*max(density1)))
    par(new=T)
    plot(x,density4,type="l",lty=4,lwd=2,xlab="",ylab="",xlim=c(bp[1],bp[N]),
        ylim=c(min(density1),2*max(density1)))
    legend("topright",legend=c("gaussian","gamma","lognormal","3-p lognormal"),

```

```

        lty=c(1,2,3,4), lwd=c(2,2,2,2))
    }
}
}

```

6.5 Script for the numeric method

What follows is the complete script discussed in par. 3.5.

```

% file name = gamma_approximation_MC
% date of creation = 17/09/2023
%
% It uses the Montecarlo method for the calculation of fY
%
clear all
close all
pkg load statistics
pkg load io
%
% start measuring time
tic;
%
pooled=[3.77,1.13,71.02,8.21,131.18,16.07]; % Stead 1945 + Barratt-Boyes 1958
%
VC23_HC_supine=[2.3,0.35,79,7,134,15]; % VanCampen 2023, HC supine
VC23_ME_supine=[2.58,0.43,80,10,138,18]; % VanCampen 2023, ME supine
VC23_HC_end_tilt=[2.04,0.28,81,8,127,14]; % VanCampen 2023, HC end-tilt
VC23_ME_end_tilt=[1.86,0.34,86,11,135,19]; % VanCampen 2023, ME end-tilt
%
VC18_HC_supine=[2.28,0.37,77,6,130,12]; % VanCampen 2018, HC supine
VC18_ME_supine=[2.38,0.36,79,9,136,18]; % VanCampen 2018, ME supine
VC18_HC_end_tilt=[2.05,0.28,81,7,126,13]; % VanCampen 2018, HC end-tilt
VC18_ME_end_tilt=[1.90,0.34,86,10,133,18]; % VanCampen 2018, ME end-tilt
%
data=cell();
data{1}=pooled;
data{2}=VC23_HC_supine;
data{3}=VC23_ME_supine;
data{4}=VC23_HC_end_tilt;
data{5}=VC23_ME_end_tilt;
data{6}=VC18_HC_supine;
data{7}=VC18_ME_supine;
data{8}=VC18_HC_end_tilt;
data{9}=VC18_ME_end_tilt;
%
name=cell();
name{1}="pooled";
name{2}="VC23_HC_supine";
name{3}="VC23_ME_supine";
name{4}="VC23_HC_end_tilt";
name{5}="VC23_ME_end_tilt";
name{6}="VC18_HC_supine";
name{7}="VC18_ME_supine";
name{8}="VC18_HC_end_tilt";
name{9}="VC18_ME_end_tilt";
%
data_i=9; %select the sample

```

```

disp(name{data_i})
m1=data{data_i}(1) % mean CI (L/min/m2)
s1=data{data_i}(2) % SD of CI
m3=data{data_i}(3) % mean of DBP (mmHg)
s3=data{data_i}(4) % SD of DBP
m4=data{data_i}(5) % mean of SBP (mmHg)
s4=data{data_i}(6) % SD of SBP
%
% array of the correlation coefficient
%
n=10;
r12(1)=0.01;
r12(n)=0.54;
d_r12=(r12(n)-r12(1))/(n-1);
for i=2:length(r12)
    r12(i) = r12(i-1)+d_r12;
endfor
m=3;
r34(1)=0.7;
r34(m)=0.8;
d_r34=(r34(m)-r34(1))/(m-1);
for i=2:length(r34)
    r34(i) = r34(i-1)+d_r34;
endfor
%
steps=400; % number of points where the densities fY and feY are evaluated
%
% mean and variance of Y=X1*X2
%
function [EY,VY,m2,s2] = mean_Y (m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r12,r34)
    m2=((2*m3)+m4)/3;
    s2=sqrt(4*s3^2 + s4^2 + 4*r34*s3*s4)/3;
    EY=r12*s1*s2+m1*m2;
    VY=(s2*m1)^2 + (s1*m2)^2 +(s1*s2)^2 + 2*r12*s1*s2*m1*m2 + (r12*s1*s2)^2;
endfunction
%
% median of Y=X1*X2
%
function [my] = median_Y (y,fY)
    i=4;
    int=0;
    while (int<0.5)
        int=trapz(y(1:i),fY(1:i));
        i=i+1;
    endwhile
    my=y(i-1);
endfunction
%
% function for calculating b
%
function [b,b0] = solve_b (EY,VY,my)
    b0 = my - 0.5*VY/(EY-my);
    b = fsolve(@(b)((my-b)^2)*(VY + (EY-b)^2) - (EY-b)^4,b0);
endfunction
%
% function for the integrand of fY
%
```

```

function integrand = func(y,s,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12)
    A=-1/(2*(1-r12^2));
    B1=(s-m1)/s1;
    B2=(y-s*m2)/(s*s2);
    B=(B1^2)-2*r12*B1*B2+(B2^2);
    C=2*pi*s1*s2*sqrt(1-r12^2);
    integrand=exp(A*B)/(C*abs(s));
endfunction
%
% density of Y by Montecarlo method
%
function fY = density_Y(y,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12)
    %
    % search for suitable extremes of integration smin and smax
    %
    cut=10^(-10);
    smin=-10;
    smax=10;
    integrand=1; % search for smin
    while(integrand>cut)
        integrand = func(y,smin,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12);
        smin=smin-1;
    endwhile
    integrand=1; % search for smax
    while(integrand>cut)
        integrand = func(y,smax,m1,m2,s1,s2,r12);
        smax=smax+1;
    endwhile
    %
    % build the uniforme random variable in [smin,smax]
    %
    steps=2000;
    s(1)=smin;
    s(steps)=smax;
    ds=(smax-smin)/(steps-1);
    s=s(1):ds:s(steps);
    %
    % Montecarlo method of integration
    %
    fY=0;
    for i=1:steps
        integrand = func(y,s(i),m1,m2,s1,s2,r12);
        fY=fY+integrand;
    endfor
    fY=((smax-smin)/steps)*fY;
endfunction
%
% density feY
%
function feY = e_density_Y (y,EY,VY,b,select)
    switch (select)
        case {1} % normal density
            feY=normpdf(y,EY,sqrt(VY));
        case {2} % gamma density
            alpha=(EY^2)/VY;
            lambda=EY/VY;
            shape=alpha;
    end
end

```

```

scale=1/lambda;
feY=gampdf(y,shape,scale);
case {3} % lognormal
    MU=log((EY^2)/sqrt(VY+EY^2));
    SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EY^2));
    feY=lognpdf(y,MU,SIGMA);
case {4} % three-parameter lognormal
    if ((y-b)<=0)
        feY=0;
    else
        EYb=EY-b;
        MU=log((EYb^2)/sqrt(VY+EYb^2));
        SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EYb^2));
        A=-0.5*((log(y-b)-MU)/SIGMA)^2;
        C=1/(SIGMA*(y-b)*sqrt(2*pi));
        feY=C*exp(A);
    endif
endswitch
endfunction
%
% function for output
%
function plotting(i,h,m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r12,r34,score,f,select,stringa,steps,name)
[EY,VY,m2,s2] = mean_Y (m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r12(i),r34(h));
y(1)=EY-4*sqrt(VY);
y(steps)=EY+4*sqrt(VY);
dy=(y(steps)-y(1))/(steps-1);
y=y(1):dy:y(steps);
%
for j=1:length(y)
    fY(j) = density_Y (y(j),m1,m2,s1,s2,r12(i));
endfor
%
[my] = median_Y (y,fY);
if (select==4)
    [b,b0] = solve_b (EY,VY,my);
else
    b=0;
endif
%
for j=1:length(y)
    feY(j) = e_density_Y (y(j),EY,VY,b,select);
endfor
figure(f)
plot(y,fY,'-k','Linewidth',1)
hold on
plot(y,feY,'-r','Linewidth',1)
xlabel('Y','FontSize',15)
ylabel('probability density','FontSize',15)
legend('f_{Y}',stringa,'FontSize',15)
str0='\rho_{1,2}=';
str1='\rho_{3,4}=';
str2='\mu_{Y}=';
str3='\{SD(Y)}=';
str4=strcat('\mu_{1}=',num2str(m1));
str5=strcat('\mu_{2}=',num2str(m2));
str6=strcat('\sigma_{1}=',num2str(s1));

```

```

str7=strcat(', {\sigma_{2}}=',num2str(s2));
str8=', score=';
str00=num2str(r12(i));
str11=num2str(r34(h));
str22=num2str(EY);
str33=num2str(sqrt(VY));
str88=num2str(score(i,h));
title(strcat(str0,str00,str1,str11,str2,str22,str3,str33,str4,str5,str6,str7,str8,str88),'FontSize',15)
grid on
grid minor
%
% write the parameters for the exact density
%
switch (select)
case {1} % normal density
    str_output="Parameters of the best normal fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY
    SD=sqrt(VY)
    my
    disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r12(i))))
    disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r34(h))))
    mu=EY
    sigma=sqrt(VY)
case {2} % gamma density
    str_output="Parameters of the best gamma fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY
    SD=sqrt(VY)
    my
    disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r12(i))))
    disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r34(h))))
    alpha=(EY^2)/VY
    lambda=EY/VY
case {3} % lognormal
    str_output="Parameters of the best lognormal fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY
    SD=sqrt(VY)
    my
    disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r12(i))))
    disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r34(h))))
    MU=log((EY^2)/sqrt(VY+EY^2))
    SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EY^2))
case {4} % three-parameter lognormal
    str_output="Parameters of the best three-parameter lognormal fit:";
    disp(strcat(name," - ",str_output))
    EY
    SD=sqrt(VY)
    my
    disp(strcat('r12=',num2str(r12(i))))
    disp(strcat('r34=',num2str(r34(h))))
    b
    EYb=EY-b;
    MU=log((EYb^2)/sqrt(VY+EYb^2))
    SIGMA=sqrt(log(1+VY/EYb^2))
endswitch

```

```

endfunction
%
% main program
%
f=0;
for select=4:4;
%
% a string for the output
%
switch (select)
case {1} % normal density
stringa = 'N(E[Y],Var[Y])';
case {2} % gamma density
stringa = '\Gamma(\alpha,\lambda)';
case {3} % lognormal
stringa = 'LogN(E[Y],Var[Y])';
case {4} % three-parameter lognormal
stringa = '3pLogN(E[Y],Var[Y],b)';
endswitch
%
% calculating score
%
counter=0;
for i=1:length(r12)
for h=1:length(r34)
[EY,VY,m2,s2] = mean_Y (m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r12(i),r34(h))
y(1)=EY-4*sqrt(VY);
y(steps)=EY+4*sqrt(VY);
dy=(y(steps)-y(1))/(steps-1);
y=y(1):dy:y(steps);
%
for j=1:length(y) % find fY
fY(j) = density_Y (y(j),m1,m2,s1,s2,r12(i));
endfor
%
[my] = median_Y (y,fY) % median of fY
if (select==4)
[b,b0] = solve_b (EY,VY,my);
else
b=0;
endif
%
for j=1:length(y) % find feY
feY(j) = e_density_Y (y(j),EY,VY,b,select);
delta_f(j) = abs(fY(j)-feY(j));
endfor
score(i,h)=trapz(y,delta_f); % area between fY, feY
counter=counter+1
endfor
endfor
%
% plot score
%
f=f+1;
figure(f)
surf(r34,r12,score)
xlabel('r_{3,4}','FontSize',15)

```

```

ylabel('r_{1,2}','FontSize',15)
title(strcat("\Delta}f, ",stringa),"fontsize",15)
%
% search for the best and worst normal approximation
%
min_score=score(1,1);
i_min=1;
h_min=1;
max_score=score(1,1);
i_max=1;
h_max=1;
for i=1:length(r12)
    for h=1:length(r34)
        if (score(i,h)<min_score)
            min_score=score(i,h);
            i_min=i;
            h_min=h;
        endif
        if (score(i,h)>max_score)
            max_score=score(i,h);
            i_max=i;
            h_max=h;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
%
Deltaf_best(select)=score(i_min,h_min);
%
% plot the best approximation
%
i=i_min;
h=h_min;
f=f+1;
plotting(i,h,m1,s1,m3,m4,s3,s4,r12,r34,score,f,select,stringa,steps,name{data_i})
endfor
%
% stop measuring time
%
elapsed_time = toc;
disp(['Elapsed time: ' num2str(elapsed_time/60) ' minutes']);

```

7 References

1. Ethier C, Simmons C. *Introductory Biomechanics*: Cambridge University Press; 2007.
2. Collia D, Zovatto L, Tonti G, Pedrizzetti G. Comparative Analysis of Right Ventricle Fluid Dynamics. *Front Bioeng Biotechnol*. 2021;9:667408.
3. Dini FL, Guarini G, Ballo P, Carluccio E, Maiello M, Capozza P, et al. The left ventricle as a mechanical engine: from Leonardo da Vinci to the echocardiographic assessment of peak power output-to-left ventricular mass. *J Cardiovasc Med (Hagerstown)*. 2013;14(3):214-20.
4. Stead EA, Warren JV, Merrill AJ, Brannon ES. THE CARDIAC OUTPUT IN MALE SUBJECTS AS MEASURED BY THE TECHNIQUE OF RIGHT ATRIAL CATHETERIZATION. NORMAL VALUES WITH OBSERVATIONS ON THE EFFECT OF ANXIETY AND TILTING. *J Clin Invest*. 1945;24(3):326-31.
5. BARRATT-BOYES BG, WOOD EH. Cardiac output and related measurements and pressure values in the right heart and associated vessels, together with an analysis of the hemo-

- dynamic response to the inhalation of high oxygen mixtures in healthy subjects. *J Lab Clin Med.* 1958;51(1):72-90.
6. Kannel WB, Gordon T, Schwartz MJ. Systolic versus diastolic blood pressure and risk of coronary heart disease. The Framingham study. *Am J Cardiol.* 1971;27(4):335-46.
 7. Gavish B, Ben-Dov IZ, Bursztyn M. Linear relationship between systolic and diastolic blood pressure monitored over 24 h: assessment and correlates. *J Hypertens.* 2008;26(2):199-209.
 8. Lie SL, Hisdal J, Høiseth L. Cerebral blood flow velocity during simultaneous changes in mean arterial pressure and cardiac output in healthy volunteers. *Eur J Appl Physiol.* 2021;121(8):2207-17.
 9. Hiemstra B, Koster G, Wiersema R, Hummel YM, van der Harst P, Snieder H, et al. The diagnostic accuracy of clinical examination for estimating cardiac index in critically ill patients: the Simple Intensive Care Studies-I. *Intensive Care Med.* 2019;45(2):190-200.
 10. Cui G, Yu X, Iommelli S, Kong L. Exact Distribution for the Product of Two Correlated Gaussian Random Variables. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters.* 2016;23(11):1662-6.
 11. Ross SM. Introduction to probability and Statistics for Engineers and Scientists 2009.
 12. van Campen C, Visser F. The Abnormal Cardiac Index and Stroke Volume Index Changes During a Normal Tilt Table Test in ME/CFS Patients Compared to Healthy Volunteers, are Not Related to Deconditioning. *J Thrombo Cir.* 2018;JTC -107.
 13. Zhou X-H, Gao S, Hui SL. Methods for Comparing the Means of Two Independent Log-Normal Samples. *Biometrics.* 1997;53(3):1129-35.
 14. Stewart JM, Pianosi P, Shaban MA, Terilli C, Svistunova M, Visintainer P, et al. Postural Hyperventilation as a Cause of Postural Tachycardia Syndrome: Increased Systemic Vascular Resistance and Decreased Cardiac Output When Upright in All Postural Tachycardia Syndrome Variants. *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2018;7(13).
 15. van Campen CLMC, Verheugt FWA, Rowe PC, Visser FC. Orthostatic chronotropic incompetence in patients with myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome (ME/CFS). *IBRO Neurosci Rep.* 2023;15:1-10.
 16. Sangal BP, Biswas AK. The 3-Parameter Lognormal Distribution and Its Applications in Hydrology. *Water Resources Research.* 1970;6(2):505-15.
 17. Maccallini P. Legge lognormale a tre parametri. 2023.
 18. Maccallini P. On the variance of the product of two correlated Gaussian random variables. 2023.
 19. Maccallini P. Variabili Aleatorie - Introduzione al Calcolo delle Probabilità e alla Statistica. 2023.